

The Development and Change of Three Local Yunnan Bands from the Perspective of Urban Music Anthropology

Fei Fei Zhang, Yimiao Su

Article Info

Article History

Received:
February 17, 2023

Accepted:
April 18, 2023

Keywords :

Local Bands,
Development And
Change, Musical Forms,
Cultural Identity,
Cultural Identity

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.7950564

Abstract

This paper selects three local bands from Yunnan Province whose music integrates innovation and heritage, focusing on the diversity of performance and music. The fusion of multi-ethnic folk tunes, songs and dances, and instrumental music frames the collision and fusion of tradition and modernity. With folk music as their foundation, the three bands have rich experience in arranging ethnic music during the transformation and change of the band's musical style, and have come out with a characteristic musical path, which has certain significance for the development of bands in Yunnan and even the whole country. Based on the fieldwork data accumulated by the author, this paper takes urban music anthropology as a perspective and adopts the methods of music ethnography, music morphology and oral history to understand the developmental changes of the three local Yunnan bands as a cultural phenomenon in terms of their development process. The specific research methods: First, the social context of the three bands' existence is explored to explore the formation, formation, transformation, and various development opportunities of the bands, as well as the driving forces behind their development. The second is to analyze their musical and instrumental compositions to understand the construction and development of their bands. This paper will also explore the development of the three bands from their formation to their formation from a dual perspective of "ephemeral-co-temporal" and "macro-micro", focusing on the development of the band during the formation period and the reasons behind it. The focus is on the development of the bands during their formative years and the reasons behind them. Through participation in performances, field trips and oral interviews with band members, we understand the events and works of the three bands, and explain the characteristics of their musical styles and cultural identities, cultural symbols and cultural identities in their regions.

Introduction

This paper will complete the literature collection from domestic and international journal or website reports, symposiums, master's degree theses, and monographs. A detailed review of the literature is done for thinking about disciplines related to urban music anthropology, traditional urban music research and local band development research, music development changes, the use of ethnic elements, music cultural identity, and music transmission and dissemination.

Urban music anthropology, a branch of music anthropology, was first proposed by the American musicologist and anthropologist Nettles in 1970. In his treatise, *Music Culture in Eight Cities: Tradition and Change*, Nettles explores the theory and methodology of the change of traditional music in urban music through issues such as musical behavior, musical forms and survival development, new cultural phenomena, different musical identity groups, musical ontology, musical styles, and social status of artists that occurred in eight cities during the modernization process.

Disciplinary Reflection On Urban Music Anthropology

Du Yaxiong (2011) proposed that traditional music in China has seen a trend of urbanization of popular territories, commercialization of performance purposes, secularization of the nature of activities, popularization of performance repertoire, and westernization of formal content with the development of urbanization, and argued that ethnomusicologists should turn their attention to the field of urban studies. Liu Shilin (2) uses different values to explore how to construct a legitimate context for the interpretation of urban music culture and suggests that using this context can lead to a better understanding of urban music and cultural phenomena. Luo Qin (2003) proposed that urban music culture is a cultural phenomenon of social development and civilization, and that music industrialization is an important cultural feature in the process of urban development. Later (Luo, 2009) summarized the development trajectory of Western anthropology and proposed a reflection and

conception of "Chinese practice" and "Chinese experience" for China's research and development in anthropology. (Luoqin, 2011) discusses urban music field research in terms of changes in the concept of "field" in music anthropology, cultural characteristics of urban music, research objects, types and categories, methodology, "near-ego experience" and "near-ego reflection" in music anthropology. The significance of urban fieldwork in music anthropology is presented in some personal reflections. Later (Luo Qin, 2017), he explains and discusses music urban research and urban music research, the content of urban music research, and the "Chinese experience" of urban music research and its methodological reflections. Xiong (2009) offers a reflection on the shape and mode of urban music anthropology and its research directions. Xue Yibing (2013) focuses on the cultural characteristics of modern urban music in China and offers constructive suggestions on the object, scope, perspective, and methodology of its study. Yu Zhong (2009) reviews the development trajectory of urban music anthropology and offers personal insights into the concerns of urban music anthropology in China.

In summary, the above mentioned scholars' references offer constructive ideas on the development history, scope of research fields, research contents, methods, phenomena, reflections, and conceptions of the discipline of urban music.

Urbanization Of Traditional Music

Fang Lei (2005) used the theory of music anthropology to compare the historical heritage changes of Norwegian folk fiddle in Norway and the United States and how to maintain the heritage. Li Xin (2001) proposed that Naxi traditional music culture faces changes brought about by urban socialization and commercialization, specifically through commercial tourism and music composition, and other aspects of the evolution of Naxi traditional music in the city. Li (2006) used the process and perspective of combing through Western research on urban music culture as an entry point to provide a feasible research methodology for the study of traditional music in Chinese cities. Li Juan (2022) uses urban music anthropology to explore the effects of Xi'an dialect songs in urbanization and their social interpretations. Guo Chuhan (2020) compares the diversity and integration of Hakka mountain songs in urban Shenzhen and suggests how to better address the dilemmas and development problems encountered in the city in order to pass on the phenomenon. Wan Zhongru (2005) used an ethnomusicological approach multidisciplinary perspective to investigate and analyze the different historical periods and musical behaviors of a folk music society. Wang, Li, and Guo, Ying (2014) reinterpreted two of the studies in Nettles' treatise and continued to explore the traditions and changes of folk music in the city, the interrelationship of the main subcultures, and the issue of cross-community and cross-territoriality transmission. Taking a representative Qin song figure as an example, Ye (2014) explores the path of transmission and development of this cultural phenomenon in the city through the social environment of the figure's existence, his life experiences, the musical form of his works, and his cultural interpretation.

In summary, the above literature presents research ideas on the development path, transmission mode, and dissemination effect of traditional music in the city.

Urban Music Landscape

Jing Ke (2012) conducted a field survey and described the musical life of Korean discrete groups in Beijing, and analyzed the phenomenon of musical transformation exhibited by cross-border communities from the perspective of music anthropology, trying to elaborate the role of music in the construction of communities. Chang Liang (2015) takes Lanzhou local pop music as the entry point and uses the Raswell model under the perspective of modern communication theory to analyze the ways to achieve the communication effect when Lanzhou local pop music is connected with external factors through the study of the communication subject, music ontology, communication channels and audience. Li Jinxia (2010) combines ethnomusicology with urban musicology and sociomusicology to investigate the development of mass opera activities in Baoding, and then explores the deep cultural foundation of traditional music culture and its positive interaction with society. Li Yue (2011) takes Baoding's community music activities as an entry point and uses urban musicology theory to examine the operation of various aspects of the interaction between music and society, revealing the positive contribution of community music as a representative of urban popular music culture to the construction of urban spiritual civilization. Ma Juan (2013) used observation and questionnaires to study the underground music in Lanzhou, and analyzed its transmitters, targets, channels, contents, and effects to provide a comprehensive picture of the cultural phenomenon. Zhang Pengfei (2009) starts from the history of street music, investigates the distribution, genres, performance forms and other basic status of the street music phenomenon in Beijing, and provides a comprehensive explanation of the interaction between street music and the Internet, the nature of street music's hooliganism, social evaluation and development status. Zhao Shufeng (2021) focuses on the issues related to urban music anthropology research, and adopts a music ethnography that combines the nature of active participation and objective observation, suggesting that the current urban music anthropology research should combine globalization and other theoretical thinking in its perspective, and the research content should be developed for the interaction of multiple elements.

In summary, urban music landscapes focus more on subcultures, gender, music industry, and music practices.

rock pop bands, societies, and new professional musicians in the urban music anthropology perspective

Chen Chen (2005) takes Shanghai as the study area, and analyzes the foundation and conditions of production and methods of local jazz in old Shanghai and new Shanghai through a comparative approach to explain the integration of Shanghai jazz with local Chinese traditional music elements. Fu Boyi (2008) compares the development, social background, and representative figures of rock music in mainland China, and uses the functional research method of "ritual" to explain the cultural values beyond the accident of music proper. He Jinxin (2017) focuses on the local development of rock music, explaining the evolution and limitations of the urbanized music of ethnic minority bands under the influence of regional culture, and proposes a reflection on this phenomenon. Wang Siqi (2005) combed through contemporary Chinese pop music culture between 1978 and 2003, highlighting important historical events as well as the social context, economy, and other factors of the time to explain the interactive influence of the cultural values and functions of contemporary pop music with the social and cultural environment. Wang Xiang (2014) selected five representative singers of different styles based on the genre of rock to explain the cultural phenomenon of youth subjects from folk-rock, collective and individual. Wu Feng (2013) sought to discover the cultural value of Filipino discrete music in our country, and proposed the construction and development of discrete music for exotic survival by explaining the notions of ethnicity and cultural identity. Using a multi-perspective and multi-disciplinary theoretical approach such as sociality, musicology, and musical anthropology, Wu Quntao (2017) punk music case studies how punk music was introduced to our country and accepted by the public. Xu Guangzhi (2019) reviewed the development of Chinese rock in the past 30 years as well as the integration of localized rock music with traditional and folk music elements through musical works to illustrate. Wang Xinzi (2019) compares the development process of rock bands in Shanxi in the mid-to-late 1990s and analyzes the musical ontology through some musical works. Solutions are proposed for the problems encountered in the development of rock bands in Shanxi at present. Xie Lirong (2008) investigated and analyzed the rock bands in Jiangsu, and systematically sorted out the problems of band existence and music creation. Later (Xie Lirong, 2009) also provides a detailed explanation of the emergence and development of bands in Nanjing since the reform and opening up, as well as the cultural phenomenon of living space. Yang Yi (2009) provides a detailed study of the current situation, identity, and cultural interpretation of the music salon in the Dongting Music Street in Hankow, which provides a case reference value for the development and transformation of traditional music in the city. Yi Rong (2009) draws on subcultural and post-subcultural theories to explain the characteristics, identity, and implications of the localization of Chinese rock music. Yao Xiaoxue (2013) takes the occupational groups in Hohhot area as the research object, and explores in depth the social changes and role reconstruction of new music occupational groups under the performance forms in different places such as restaurants, bars and scenic spots.

To sum up, the above cases explain the development basis, causes and value impact of different groups in the process of urban cultural development through the research method of urban music anthropology with different research objects and interdisciplinary theories. The regional and localized development of music is highlighted in the process of research content, which provides research ideas and creative directions for the author's thesis. However, the above research contents are concerned with music ontology, current development, and lack of inheritance and continuity strategies for the future.

The Issue Of Musical Change

Cao Hua (2015) traced the cultural trajectory and aesthetic flow of popular songs in mainland China over the thirty years from 1978-2014. Three levels of subject image, spiritual gesture, and cultural consciousness are used to find the refraction of chemistry in the lyrics; the author argues that the observation of the relationship between music and the times, music and society, and music and spirituality can be concluded from the cultural and aesthetic fluxes over the thirty years from 1978-2014. Only by reflecting the local human spirit in composing songs will there not be works that lack value in the midst of cultural changes.

Chen Guofu (2020) focuses on the causes of the loss of traditional music of the indigenous ethnic groups in Sabah, East Malaysia, and finds that the tourism industry has led to a renewed interest in local traditional music among local residents, and reflects on the issue of the transmission and development of local traditional music in the midst of change. Deng Zixin et al. (2020) used the CCTV Spring Festival Gala program as an object to reflect the changes and development of society based on the content of the subject matter created by the popular song program. Hu Bin (2009) takes the development of the guqin in Shanghai over the past hundred years as the object of study, and compiles the changes in the functions, cultural subject roles, expressions, and symbolic meanings of the guqin during the urbanization of Shanghai in different periods. Liu Zhenyin (2007) compares the compositional characteristics of the representatives of the three East Asian composers in the face of the influence of Western culture in different periods, summarizes and concludes the musical changes in the three countries, and proposes that the Western influence is not a Westernized view. Liu Hui (2008) looks at the

change of musical styles over time, space, and social environment in the context of the historical development of musical anthropology. Li Jianrong (2012) explored the modern musical changes of Yunnan's ethnic groups in terms of their cultural habitat, musical heritage, and musical forms. Liu Fujun (2013) used the sociological perspective of music to explore how the reform and opening up and the modern development process of the country have influenced the socio-cultural changes of the Yi ethnic group, thus affecting the changes of musical styles, themes, and functions of the songs in the region at the same time. Li Shanna (2013) combed through the historical trajectory of Lisu Christian music and dance and made an evolutionary analysis of the functions of traditional rituals.

Sun Mei (2021) focuses on the socio-cultural space of the Honghe Hani, from village traditions to eight voices, interviewing bearers and experts and scholars to explore the musical changes of this cultural phenomenon. Wang Jingyi (2003) elaborates on the traditional musical sources and culturally generated conditions of the Chinese in Malaysia, and also provides a detailed overview of the modes of transmission and musical style changes. Wu Jiawen (2008) uses the case study of the two-string inheritors to illustrate the changes in the mode of inheritance according to the identity of the inheritors in different periods. Zheng Huaqiu and Zheng Xianshang (2017) compared two different traditional musical instruments from Vietnam and Indonesia, and looked at the developmental changes of the instruments from their production, shape, use to functional changes. Zhang Yufan (2021) looks at the changes and causes of female image through female talent shows in different eras in China, which both reflect the issue of changing social gender discourse.

Books on Yunnan minority and traditional music terminology explained:

Cao Liping (2014) proposed that Chinese pop music must take the path of music creation with ethnicity and localization in order to be loved by the nation, and this style of music can achieve sustainable development in China and even internationally. Chen Shixiang (2018) introduced the significance of folk music elements in pop music composition, the way they are used, and their significance to the trend of nationalization of contemporary pop music. Fan Yanping (2022) pointed out that the introduction of folk music elements in contemporary music creation can largely enrich the connotation of contemporary music works, enrich the performance skills of music works, and meet the aesthetic needs of modern people.

Feng Shuoguo (2017) proposes that the elements of Jingpo tonality are used in the creation of popular music, which is loved and paid attention to by the public. This not only represents the ethnic cultural identity but also about the harmony and unity of the community. Liang Meiling (2020) classifies the functions of liner notes in Yi folk songs and suggests that the study of liner notes is actually an exploration of Yi music culture, which is conducive to the promotion and inheritance of Yi folk song culture and deepens more scholars' knowledge of Yi folk songs. Lu Jufang (2021) studied the musical form of songs in the Yi Adu Torch Festival ritual with distinctive ethnic surname song cadences and found that there is a lineage relationship with the ethnic song cadences prevalent in the development of Nosu music mentioned by him.

Liu Xingyun (2015) points out that the "I am a Singer" program draws on the excellent Chinese traditional culture in the selection of singers, and produces positive effects through the use of ethnic music elements, which plays a better role as a model for reality TV shows. To a certain extent, it has promoted the good development of popular music and brought into play the social function and value of art.

Luo Jinjun (2014) emphasizes that the diversified development of pop music will also make the development market of music broader, not only save the domestic market, but also open the foreign market, make the closed traditional music to open, and make the pop music with single and monologue creation become more rich and connotative.

By listing representative singers from different periods in the history of Chinese pop music development, Li Longzhu (2012) elaborates on the changes in pop music after the spread of its creation in different regions of China. It is proposed that local pop music in China needs to be combined with local humanities and traditional culture to provide theoretical support and new ideas for pop creators.

Mi Jie (2017) found that Chinese national traditional music is gradually being left behind for many reasons, and pop music can be integrated into national music elements in the development process, making pop music more flavorful and enabling national music to be passed on, and the two should take the essence and remove the dross, integrate and improve each other in order to better inherit and develop national music and pop music, and also to make traditional music and pop music more aesthetically pleasing.

Mou Hua (2019) compares the historical lineage of the development of pop music in China and the West, emphasizing that pop music carries distinctive characteristics of urbanization, industrialization, and profitability, and fits in with urban and social development. He proposes that pop music is a cultural and economic phenomenon, a commodity and an art, and that the creation of pop music should pay attention to the artistry, communication and ideology of music in the face of the market, and make a good balance among them in order to make it develop sustainably.

Qian Cheng (2015) discusses the Chinese piano piece "Doyle", a collection of modern music, and concludes that folk music provides a lot of materials for the creation of Chinese modern music, and the application of

modern composition techniques makes the folk music elements show in a new musical form, and then form modern music with obvious Chinese elements to promote the development of Chinese music.

Shi Yong (2015) provides an in-depth analysis of different kinds and styles of music pieces from several aspects of composition roots, composition conceptions, and composition meanings and presents his own understanding of musical works. He proposes that tradition and pop should not lack the aesthetics, tuning and singing style of traditional music, but also the tuning style and aesthetics of pop music, and they should promote each other, so that traditional music can be inherited and pop music can be promoted.

Shi Yong (2017) selects nearly one hundred Chinese pop music songs and discusses a category of Chinese pop songs with distinctive Chinese traditional music cultural styles and musical forms in the context of regional cultural divisions and ethnic minority cultural divisions in Chinese traditional music, which are typically representative and of cultural research value.

Tian Ye (2015) points out that through his musical compositions, Yin Qing integrates ethnic factors and forms his unique artistic style. By analyzing the musical works of Yin Qing, it shows that music creation should be built among the culture of the nation, and the application of ethnic elements can play a positive role in the creation and have an impact on the inheritance and development of the traditional culture of ethnic music.

Wang Dan (2017) studies how composers of different compositional styles are using Yunnan minority music to fuse in different kinds of modern music compositions, while pointing out that this new artistic approach, in today's context, not only responds to the needs of the times, but also inherits and promotes the traditional culture of the Chinese nation, promotes the development and progress of musical forms, and provides more people who love music with richer means of expression.

Wang Zhe (2016) emphasizes that the current development trend of popular music is the fusion and development of traditional folk ethnic music and popular music, and the creation of songs is reflected in the use of ethnic tunes, melodic fragments, the use of ethnic minority poems and ethnic operas, and the effective use of fusion in singing styles and musical arrangements, so that works in this form can make ethnic music more effectively spread and inheritance.

Xue, Lina (2017) compares two local bands in terms of identity, music creation philosophy, music style, and artistic experience to study how the two bands fuse Zhuang music elements with popular music creation. Although the two bands are very different in musical styles, they are both well liked by the general audience in different degrees and acceptance, and play a role in spreading and passing on Zhuang music culture.

Yang Yuyue buckwheat (2018) takes the perspective of the musical composition of the band Tianjue and Pestle as an entry point, and looks at how the melody, song style, rhythm, singing style, instrumental performance techniques, and orchestration in the work to see how the Tibetan music elements are integrated and created with Western pop music. We also discover the meaning and value of their creation, and at the same time provide creators with new ideas of creation, from the technical means can support the creative thinking in a deeper level.

(a) Research on Yunnan minority music: Musicologist Su Yimiao published "Field Investigation and Reflections on the Hua-waist Yi Folk Song "Ari" in Shiping, Yunnan," "Crossing the Sacred and the Mundane," "Sacred and Carnival on the Day of the Horse," "The Role and Representation of Women in Ritual Music," and "The Legacy of the Pre-Qin Ritual Society. --The "Flower Children's Meeting" and the "Dragon Ritual" of the Huawei Yi in Erlang Mountain, Minxian County" and other papers have been published in the Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music, Chinese Musicology, Chinese Music and other journals. The paper was published in the Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music, Chinese Music, Chinese Music, Ethnic Arts, etc. Musicologist Zhang Xingrong has done in-depth research on Yunnan's folk instrumental music, cave scripture culture, and original folk music, as follows:

Su Yimiao (2010) explored the survival and development mode of the "Ari" in terms of its origin, musical form, and inheritance characteristics of the Huashou Yi folk song in Shiping, Yunnan. (Su, Yimiao, 2011) used musical anthropology to analyze the musical attributes of the dragon ritual of the Hua-waist Yi in Shuiguan-chong Village, Shuanchong Town, Shiping County, Yunnan Province to explore the significance of this culture. (Su, Yimiao, 2011) used a musical ethnography to reveal the cultural connotations of the funeral rituals of the Nisu Huayi. In the study of inheritance, Su Yimiao analyzed the Yi "Ari", the Nisu-Huayao "Dragon Ritual", and the "Quzi Master" of the Haicai cavity, which are the mapping of the inheritance patterns of the Yi culture in southern Yunnan. In the area of cross-border music research, (Su Yi Miao), he has interpreted the historical dimension, social maintenance, and individual creation of Yi culture inheritance patterns. In the study of cross-border music: (Su Yimiao, 2016) studied the cadences of the Yi "chanting" in China and Vietnam, followed by a series of studies on the logical relationship between the scriptures and lyrics, the migration paths of ethnic groups, and the identification of ethnic names, which revealed the bloodline connection between the Yi Nisu people of South Yunnan and the toms of North Vietnam.

(b) Regarding the research on Yunnan's ethnic instrumental music: Bian Yue (2017) the author used literature research method, comparative research method and fieldwork method to develop the exploration, combining theory and practice to analyze the research object. In-depth research is conducted on the Yi Yueqin

production process in Yao'an County, comparing the similarities and differences between the Han and Yi Yueqin in terms of production processes and application functions. The problems in the production and inheritance of the Yueqin craft are suggested to enhance both the ethnic cultural identity and recognition at the cultural level, and the cultural environment to strengthen the care and cultivation of talents. Ma Zhenwei (2020) focuses on the development history of the Zani grand sanshin, and makes a detailed review of its instrumental sources and characteristics classification, and interprets the history of changes in the production techniques of its Zani grand sanshin, the production techniques and the totemic culture therein. The pairs of strings, functions, and representatives of artists of the Dasanshin are explained in detail, and effective measures for two-way protection by the government and folk are proposed in the face of the present-day inheritance and protection of the Dasanshin of Sani. Rao Shujian (2016) elaborates on the local Yueqin production in Nanhua and Muding counties in the Chuxiong Yi region of Yunnan, and conducts a comparative study of the origin of the Yueqin in the Central Plains and the origin of the Yueqin in the Yi region. The article focuses on the historical origin and development of the Yueqin, the production of the Yueqin, the performance of the Yueqin, and the social function and preservation and transmission of the Yueqin, and explores the contemporary historical and cultural value, social value, and even aesthetic value of the Yueqin. The book by Zhang Xingrong (1986) is a reflection on the historical and cultural value, social value, and even aesthetic and economic value of the Yueqin.

Zhang Xingrong's (1986) *Selected Ethnic Instrumental Music of Western Yunnan* published a selection of scores of different instrumental music from Yunnan Province, followed by (Zhang Xingrong, 1990) a treatise, *A Collection of Ethnic Instrumental Music of Yunnan*, which included 24 ethnic minority instruments from Yunnan with photographs and explanations of their performance venues and functional uses, as well as brief notes from folk artists. Under the category of instrumental music, *The Legends of Yunnan's Instrumental Kingdom* presents legends and stories about instrumental music according to Yunnan's minority groups, along with some representative instrumental music. Li Yue (2011) takes Baoding's community music activities as an entry point and uses urban musicology theory to examine the operation of various aspects of the interaction between music and society, revealing the positive contribution of community music as a representative of urban popular music culture to the construction of urban spiritual civilization. Ma Juan (2013) used observation and questionnaires to study the underground music in Lanzhou, and analyzed its transmitters, targets, channels, contents, and effects to provide a comprehensive picture of the cultural phenomenon.

Zhang Pengfei (2009) starts from the history of street music, investigates the distribution, genres, performance forms and other basic status of the street music phenomenon in Beijing, and provides a comprehensive explanation of the interaction between street music and the Internet, the nature of street music's hooliganism, social evaluation and development status.

Zhao Shufeng (2021) focuses on the issues related to urban music anthropology research, and adopts a music ethnography that combines the nature of active participation and objective observation, suggesting that the current urban music anthropology research should combine globalization and other theoretical thinking in its perspective, and the research content should be developed for the interaction of multiple elements.

In summary, urban music landscapes focus more on subcultures, gender, music industry, and music practices. (d) Studies on rock pop bands, societies, and new professional musicians in the urban music anthropology perspective are as follows: Chen Chen (2005) takes Shanghai as the study area, and analyzes the foundation and conditions of production and methods of local jazz in old Shanghai and new Shanghai through a comparative approach to explain the integration of Shanghai jazz with local Chinese traditional music elements. Fu Boyi (2008) compares the development, social background, and representative figures of rock music in mainland China, and uses the functional research method of "ritual" to explain the cultural values beyond the accident of music proper.

He Jinxin (2017) focuses on the local development of rock music, explaining the evolution and limitations of the urbanized music of ethnic minority bands under the influence of regional culture, and proposes a reflection on this phenomenon.

Wang Siqi (2005) combed through contemporary Chinese pop music culture between 1978 and 2003, highlighting important historical events as well as the social context, economy, and other factors of the time to explain the interactive influence of the cultural values and functions of contemporary pop music with the social and cultural environment.

Wang Xiang (2014) selected five representative singers of different styles based on the genre of rock to explain the cultural phenomenon of youth subjects from folk-rock, collective and individual.

Wu Feng (2013) sought to discover the cultural value of Filipino discrete music in our country, and proposed the construction and development of discrete music for exotic survival by explaining the notions of ethnicity and cultural identity.

Discussion

Using a multi-perspective and multi-disciplinary theoretical approach such as sociality, musicology, and musical anthropology, Wu Quntao (2017) punk music case studies how punk music was introduced to our

country and accepted by the public. Xu Guangzhi (2019) reviewed the development of Chinese rock in the past 30 years as well as the integration of localized rock music with traditional and folk music elements through musical works to illustrate. Wang Xinzi (2019) compares the development process of rock bands in Shanxi in the mid-to-late 1990s and analyzes the musical ontology through some musical works. Solutions are proposed for the problems encountered in the development of rock bands in Shanxi at present. Xie Lirong (2008) investigated and analyzed the rock bands in Jiangsu, and systematically sorted out the problems of band existence and music creation.

Later (Xie Lirong, 2009) also provides a detailed explanation of the emergence and development of bands in Nanjing since the reform and opening up, as well as the cultural phenomenon of living space. Yang Yi (2009) provides a detailed study of the current situation, identity, and cultural interpretation of the music salon in the Dongting Music Street in Hankow, which provides a case reference value for the development and transformation of traditional music in the city.

Yi Rong (2009) draws on subcultural and post-subcultural theories to explain the characteristics, identity, and implications of the localization of Chinese rock music. Yao Xiaoxue (2013) takes the occupational groups in Hohhot area as the research object, and explores in depth the social changes and role reconstruction of new music occupational groups under the performance forms in different places such as restaurants, bars and scenic spots. To sum up, the above cases explain the development basis, causes and value impact of different groups in the process of urban cultural development through the research method of urban music anthropology with different research objects and interdisciplinary theories. The regional and localized development of music is highlighted in the process of research content, which provides research ideas and creative directions for the author's thesis. However, the above research contents are concerned with music ontology, current development, and lack of inheritance and continuity strategies for the future. 2.1.2 Relevant literature on the issue of musical change is sorted out:

Cao Hua (2015) traced the cultural trajectory and aesthetic flow of popular songs in mainland China over the thirty years from 1978-2014. Three levels of subject image, spiritual gesture, and cultural consciousness are used to find the refraction of chemistry in the lyrics; the author argues that the observation of the relationship between music and the times, music and society, and music and spirituality can be concluded from the cultural and aesthetic fluxes over the thirty years from 1978-2014. Only by reflecting the local human spirit in composing songs will there not be works that lack value in the midst of cultural changes.

Chen Guofu (2020) focuses on the causes of the loss of traditional music of the indigenous ethnic groups in Sabah, East Malaysia, and finds that the tourism industry has led to a renewed interest in local traditional music among local residents, and reflects on the issue of the transmission and development of local traditional music in the midst of change. Deng Zixin et al. (2020) used the CCTV Spring Festival Gala program as an object to reflect the changes and development of society based on the content of the subject matter created by the popular song program.

Conclusion

In terms of the historical background and definition of ethnomusicology, the authors propose that ethnomusicology is a composite term, formed by combining two parts, ethnology and musicology, to form a separate disciplinary vocabulary, so that it contains both ethnographic disciplinary content and musicological disciplinary categories. The authors focus on the interactive influences of ethnomusicology with the disciplines, such as the relationship and position of ethnomusicology with several separate disciplines: anthropology, ethnography, sociology, folklore, geography, and linguistics. Next, the methodological perspectives of ethnomusicology, including the methodological perspectives of subjectivity, values, and spatio-temporality, as well as the theories and methods of fieldwork, musical description and musical interpretation in ethnomusicology, a range of disciplinary findings in ethnomusicology, and so on, are presented separately. With this narrative, the authors argue that the study of ethnomusicology is actually intended to provide a comprehensive and complete general overview of the discipline, presenting learners with a methodological perception and examination of the discipline in its larger cultural context and environment, thus allowing the discipline to be gradually constructed, formed, and refined.

References

- Bian Yue (2017). Research on the production process of Yi Yueqin in Yao'an County [Master's thesis]. Yunnan Agricultural University.
- Cao, Hua (2015). Cultural trajectory and aesthetic flux of popular songs in mainland China (1978-2014) [Doctoral dissertation]. Jinan University.
<https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CDFDLAST2022&filename=1015979083.nh>
- Cao, L.P. (2014). The borrowing and application of folk music elements in Chinese pop music. *Northern Music*, (08), 190.
- Chen, S. (2018). Analyzing the use of folk music elements in pop music composition. *Northern Music*, (08), 10.
- Chen, W. Q. (2014). The use of folk music elements in popular music. *Northern Music*, (11), 26-36.
- Dong, Weisong (1987). On traditional Chinese music and its classification. *Chinese music*, (02).
- Dong, Chen (2017). A study on music and identification with the sound pattern of class chanting in Southern Buddhist Pali. *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (02), 30-40. doi:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2017.02.004
- Fan, Yanping (2022). The presentation of folk music elements in contemporary music. *Theatre House*, (03), 81-82.
- Feng, Shuoguo (2017). Research on the integration of Jingpo "ethnic tones" and popular music [Master's thesis]. Yunnan Academy of Arts.
<https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201801&filename=1017193993.nh>
- Guo X (2018). The "ethnic tones" and development of Yunnan Jingpo music from the perspective of ethnic cultural identity. *Guizhou Ethnic Studies*, (05). doi:10.13965/j.cnki.gzmzyj10026959.2018.05.018
- Hu, Yan (2018). A study of ethnic music elements in Chinese popular music. *Northern Music*, (1), 26-27.
- Li Kunsheng and Zhou Wenlin, eds. (2002). *Yunnan minority costumes*. Yunnan Fine Arts Publishing House.
- Li, Longzhu (2012). An analysis of the ethnicization of Chinese pop music composition. *Journal of Heilongjiang Oriental College*, *Northern Music* (03), 45-46.
- Li, Xiaoyan (2009). Ethnic music elements in popular music. *Ethnic music research*, (06), 82-83.
- Li, Yue (2015). The use of folk music elements in the creation of popular music works. *Northern Music*, (02), 164.
- Liang, M. L. (2020). A preliminary investigation on the function and use of lining words in Yi folk songs. *Journal of Honghe College*, (05), 29-31+35. doi:10.13963/j.cnki.hhxb.2020.05.008.
- Liu, F. (2016). A study of Jay Chou's music in the perspective of ethnomusicology [Master's thesis]. Northwest University for Nationalities.
<https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201701&filename=1016313191.nh>
- Liu, X.Y. (2015). On the use and communication value of ethnomusicological elements in singing reality shows - Taking "I am a singer" as an example. *Art Education*, (12), 40-41.
- Liu, Zhengwei (2004). The genetic genes of music: Five states, four paths and three lines of traditional music. *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (03), 31-39+48. doi:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2004.03.007
- Lu, J. F. (2021). Ethnicity song cadence - A comparative study of the musical forms of the Yi Adu Torch Festival ritual. *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (04), 15-30. doi:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2021.04.002
- Luo, Jinjun (2014). An analysis of the role of traditional music elements in the creation of popular music and their influence. *Northern Music*, (09), 174.
- Lv, C.C., Liu, Shufeng, Ma, Huiqin, and Zeng, S.O. (1991). *Dictionary of Chinese minority arts*. Nationalities Press.
- Ma, Zhenwei (2020). The production techniques and "vitalization" process of the three major Zani strings [Master's thesis]. China Conservatory of Music.
- Mao, Mina (2019). Exploration of Chinese folk music elements and popular music elements: A conception of music composition for the one-act play "Bodhi Green Snake" by National Arts Foundation. *Drama House*, (02), 45-47.
- Mi, J. (2017). Analysis of folk music elements in Chinese popular music. *Northern Music*, (05), 44-48.
- Miao, J. H. (2017). Ewenki music culture construction and identity-Example of Bayan Hushuo Ovoo sacrifice. *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (02), 19-29. doi:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2017.02.003
- Mou, H. (2019). *Introduction to the development of Chinese and Western popular music*. China Textile Press.
- Pan, ZJ (2017). Exploring the integration between folk music elements and modern composition techniques. *Northern Music*, (21), 254.
- Peng Zhaorong (1999). Ethnic identity and the occurrence of music. *Journal of Chinese Musicology*, (03).
- Qian, C. (2015). Exploring the integration of ethnic music elements and modern composition techniques. *Art Research*, (01), 170-171. doi:10.13944/j.cnki.ysyj.2015.0077
- Qiao, J. C. (2009). *Traditional Chinese music*. Shanghai Music Publishing House.

- Rao, Shujian (2016). Research on Chuxiong Yi Yueqin [Master's thesis]. Central University for Nationalities.
<https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201701&filename=1016134915.nh>
- Ren Fei (2012). Research on Chinese contemporary pop music in the field of communication [Doctoral dissertation]. Shandong University.
<https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CDFDLAST2022&filename=1013140591.nh>
- Shi Jonze (2020). Identity, ethnic unity and social integration: An anthropological interpretation of the soul calling ceremony of the Wengding Wa. *Journal of Honghe College*, 18(2), 47-50+53.
 DOI:10.13963/j.cnki.hhxb.2020.02.013
- Shi, Wing (2015). The use of Chinese folk instrumental pieces in pop music composition. *People's Music*, (07), 74-78.
- Shi, Wing (2017). A guide to the appreciation of Chinese pop songs. Anhui Literature and Art Publishing House.
- Su Man (2019). Research on the dissemination strategy of Mongolian music - taking Hanggai band as an example [Master's thesis]. Jinan University.
<https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD202101&filename=1020705667.nh>
- Tian Ye (2015). The use of ethnic music elements in Indochine music composition. *Music Creation*, (03), 113-115.
- Wang, D. (2017). Exploration on the application of Yunnan folk music elements in professional songwriting [Master's thesis]. Yunnan Normal University.
<https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201801&filename=1017730826.nh>
- Wang, F. (2015). The integration of folk music elements in modern pop music. *Northern Music*, (04), 30.
- Wang, Hansong (2020). Research on Chinese pop music - Analysis of the integration of folk music elements in Chinese pop singing. *Journal of Dalian University*, 41(02), 102-105.
- Wang, L. (2014). Experimental discussion on the nationalized elements in Chinese pop music composition. *Music Creation*, (09), 127-129.
- Wang, Meng Z. (2021). On the Contextual Beauty of Ethnomusicological Elements in Zhao Jiping's "Symphony of Fengyasong". *Journal of Zhoukou Normal College*, 38(04), 141-144+150.
 doi:10.13450/j.cnki.jzknu.2021.04.27
- Wang, Che (2016). Analysis of the use of folk music elements in popular music [Master's thesis]. Hebei University.
<https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201701&filename=1016762638.nh>
- Wei, Linlin (2017). Context and identity of daily music practice in the mixed Mongolian-Chinese area-Example of the singing of the song "Kissing duodai" in the cultural compound of Tuoyu Banner. *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (2), 55. doi:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2017.02.007
- Wei Zheng (2018). Research on the mechanism of Wa music transmission under the perspective of cultural identity. *Guizhou Ethnic Studies*, (03), 72-75. doi:10.13965/j.cnki.gzmzyj10026959.2018.03.017
- Wu, G. (2012). Introduction to ethnomusicology. People's Music Publishing House.
- Xie, Chong Lyr and Xie, Zilu (2012). The music of China's Yunnan minority people examines sources. Shanghai Sanlian Bookstore.
- Xue, Lina (2017). The fusion of ethnic traditional music and popular music: the example of two Guangxi Zhuang pop bands [Master's thesis]. Guangxi University for Nationalities.
- Yang, M.K. (2017). The study of Chinese minority music in the context of "music and identity"-moderator's remarks on "music and identity". *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (02), 3-11.
 DOI:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2017.02.001.
- Yang, Xifan (2017). The authority of metaphor-A study on the cultural identity of Bai cave sutra music. *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (02), 12-18. doi:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2017.02.002
- Yang, Y. Buckwheat (2018). The fusion of Tibetan folk music elements in popular music styles: the example of the band Tianjue and Pestle [Master's thesis]. Nanjing Arts College.
- Zeng Suijin (2013). Tutorial of music communication theory. Communication University of China Press.
- Zhang L. (2020). A study of cultural identity and cultural power of the Liangshan Yi people in the context of modernity. *Journal of Honghe College*, 18(1), 44-46. doi:10.13963/j.cnki.hhxb.2020.01.010
- Zhang, L. Y. (2015). Ethnic music elements in Chinese popular music. *Northern Music*, (07), 36-38.
- Zhang, Lin (2017). Cultural identity in music construction: An example of "Manchu traditional ritual music" in Xinbin. *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (02), 47-54. doi:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2017.02.006
- Zhang, Yang and Huo, Yulei (2020). The integration of traditional folk music elements in modern composition. *Journal of Hehe College*, (10), 152-153+172.
- Zhang, C.-S. (1989). The "ethnicity song" of the Shui ethnic group and its variation - an exploration of the melodic structure of ethnic music. *Chinese Music*, (03).

- Zhao, Shufeng (2017). Ethnic boundaries and musical identity: An anthropological interpretation of the music of the "Noisy Party" of the Manchu people in Fengning, Hebei. *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (02), 41-46.
DOI:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2017.02.005.
- Zhao, Shufeng (2020). Ethnicity construction and cultural identity of Pingdi Yao music at the border of Xiang and Gui. *Journal of the Central Conservatory of Music*, (02), 14-27. doi:10.16504/j.cnki.cn11-1183/j.2020.02.002
- Zhou, Xiaoyan (2013). A study of Chinese popular music in the cultural perspective [Master's thesis]. Suzhou University.
<https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CDFD1214&filename=1013230179.nh>
- Zheng, X. Y. (1992). *Cultural identity and cultural change*. China Social Science Press.

Author Information

Fei Fei Zhang

International College, Krirk University Thailand

Yimiao SuInternational College, Krirk University Thailand
